

MECHANICAL PROPERTY AND FRACTURE BEHAVIOR OF THERMOSETTING FRP REINFORCED CARBON FIBERS AND PAPERBOARD

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Keywords: Fracture behavior, FRP, Paperboard, Recycled fibers

ABSTRACT

Deforestation is a big problem to the world. It has negative effects to the atmosphere, water cycle, soil and biodiversity. The usage of paperboard can release the needs to the timber. Furthermore, the paper recycling is an effective way to reduce garbage and reused limited resources. However the mechanical property of paperboard limits its applications. In the previous research, the recycled paperboard and thermosetting resin was used to fabricate paperboard composite. The mechanical property was test and got a good result. In this research is hybrid paperboards were manufactured with poly ethylene (PE) fibers, carbon fibers and jute fibers by paper making method. Then the hybrid paperboards were used to fabricate fiber reinforced plastic (FRP) with unsaturated polyester resin as well as recycled paperboard. Tensile property and bending property of these materials was investigated. The property was evaluated between hybrid carbon FRP and paperboard FRP. The materials expressed obviously anisotropic property. The main difference between different directions was considered due to the fibers orientation which was determined by the fabricating process. From scanning electron microscope (SEM) observation, it was found that the carbon fibers were pulled out in the carbon FRP case. It seems that the resin in the FRP is insufficient. The fracture of bending specimens were also investigated.

1 INTRODUCTION

Paperboards are thick papers made of wood, chemical pulp waster paper, etc. The manufacturing method of paperboards is similar to papers'. In this method, the plant fibers are dispersed in the water and carried by big web rolls to dehydrate and to dry.

Several tanks and big web rolls is used to manufacture paperboard, so the paperboards are laminated materials. By this method different fibers can be used in different layers and each layer of paperboard can use mixed fibers so as to hybrid paperboard mat can be manufactured. It is considered that the original paperboards has anisotropic property mat due to paper fibers has different distribution on different orientation which is formed during fabrication process. At current study, carbon fibers or jute fibers was used to manufacture paperboard materials. Carbon fiber or jute fibers were mixed with resin fibers (Poly Ethylene) for each layers of paperboards.

After fabrication of paperboards, paperboard fiber reinforced plastic (FRP) was fabricated with unsaturated polyester resin. Mechanical properties included tension, bending and Izod impact properties were tested and analyzed.

2 MATERIALS AND EXPERIMENTS

2.1 Materials

Carbons were cut before using by a cutter with 6mm-diameter of strainer and jute fibers were also cut by a cutter with 2mm-diameter of strainer. In this study, the basic paper pulp was recycled milk package which was used in 40 wt%. Carbon fibers or jute fibers were used in 30 wt%. Resin fibers were in 30 wt%. Paperboards made of paper fibers and PE fibers were used as a comparison. The materials composition is shown in table 1. The direction along production line was defined as MD and the transverse direction was defined as TD. Four kinds of paperboard were used here, included PE hybrid paperboard, recycled milk package paperboard, carbon hybrid paperboards and jute hybrid paperboard. The photo of these paperboard is shown in figure 1.

Table 1 Contents of each paperboard

	Materials wt%			
	Milk pulp	PE fibers	Carbon	Jute
PE	40 %	60	0	0
Paper	100 %	0	0	0
Carbon	40 %	30 %	30 %	0
Jute	40 %	30 %	0	30 %

Figure 1 Four kinds of paperboards

Unsaturated polyester resin (150HRBQNTNW, produced by Showa Highpolymer Co.Ltd) was used as matrix in this study. (Polymer was mixed with the hardener MEKPO (PERMEK N; NOF Corporation) in a ratio of 100:0.7). The Young's modulus and tensile strength are 3.2GPa and 42.0 MPa respectively.

2.2 Composite fabrication and specimens preparation

The composite plate was fabricated by hand lay-up method. One layer and 6 layers laminates were preparation for tensile and bending respectively. The special steps were as follows: first, did the preparation and mixed the resin and hardener in the ratio of 100:0.7, then put a piece of plastic paper on the iron plate; second, put some resin on the plastic paper then put the paperboard above the resin and make the resin impregnate the paperboard with a small roller, after that ,resin was put on the paperboard and went on making the resin impregnate the paperboard, after finishing that, cover the paperboard FRP with another piece of plastic paper. After fabrication, the materials were disposed on steel moulds in 24 hours for cure. Post cure was followed in the condition of 100 °C maintained 2 hours.

2.3 Fibers distribution of paperboard

The optical observation of three kinds of paperboard and hybrid paperboard FRP is shown in figure 2.

Figure 2 Optical observation of paperboard, carbon fiber mat and jute fiber mat

From the observation, it was found the some bundle cannot be dispersed during fabricating process which was considered would be limited the materials properties. For jute fibers big bundle also can be found.

2.4 Mechanical properties

Tensile test was conducted on both notched and unnotched specimens in this research. The composites were cut into the design size according to Japanese Industrial Standards (JIS K7113 and JIS K7085). Tensile test was performed by using an Instron universal testing machine under a speed of 1 mm/min. An extensometer was used to measure the strain during tensile process. Both MD and TD was tested. To make notched specimens, 10 mm hole were drilled in the geometric center of the specimens with drills from H.A.M. PRECISION TOOLS (Type: 342) at the speed of 2300 rad/min. The dimension of the unnotched specimens was 200×20 mm, the dimension of the notched specimens was 200 ×30 mm, and the span of each specimen was 100 mm.

The bending test was also performed by using the universal testing machine under a speed of 1 mm/min. The dimension of the specimens was 80×15×4 mm and the span was 64 mm.

Izod impact test was performed on the Impact Tester (Toyoseiki), pendulum 5.5J, in accordance with ADTM D 256-05. The size of the specimen was 10mm×60mm, V-notch was used: the angle of the notch was 45°. The depth of notch is 2mm.

2.5 Acoustic emission (AE) measurement

The AE testing equipment and test parameters were as follows: Physical Acoustic corporation Micro-30 sensors; 26dB preamplifiers having a bandwidth of 65 - 1100 KHz; system threshold of 25 dB; Peak definition time of 50; hit definition time of 150; hit lockout time of 300 .After setting, the AE signals were captured during mechanical testing by the software named “AE win for USB”.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Tensile property

Stress-strain curve of paperboard FRP together with acoustic emission measurement results are shown in figure 3. This result indicates that the paperboard FRP has obvious anisotropic property. This phenomenon is mainly effected by the fibers orientation decided by manufacture process of paperboard. Compared with TD specimens, MD specimens have bigger breaking elongation. In the reference [1], different events occurred inside the materials included fiber-matrix interfacial debonding, matrix plastic deformation and cracking, fiber pull-out, fiber breakage and interlaminar delamination was distinguished from acoustic emission events amplitude range 30-45 dB (low amplitude events), 30-60 dB (low amplitude events), 60-80 dB (middle amplitude events), 80-97 (high amplitude events)

and 60-85 dB (middle amplitude events), respectively. Compared others, carbon fiber composite generated more damage inside materials during tensile test.

Figure 3 Stress-strain curve of tensile test with AE results

The results of Young’s modulus and tensile strength is shown in figure 4. From this results, it was found that recycled paperboard has the highest Young’s modulus and tensile strength. The Young’s modulus and tensile strength are 12.3 GPa and 110 Mpa respectively. The carbon hybrid FRP, jute hybrid composite and PE hybrid composite are lower in sequence. At the same time, the anisotropic property of each type materials is confirmed.

Figure 4 Tensile results

3.2 Bending test

The load-deflection curve from bending test is shown in figure 5.

Figure 5 Load-deflection curve of bending test

After fabricating, the thickness of different FRPs were different. As a results it is difficult to compared bending strength from load-deflection curves. The thicknesses are 3.15mm, 4.67mm and 4.06mm for paperboard FRP, carbon hybrid FRP and Jute hybrid FRP respectively. However from the load-deflection curves, it is found

that the deflection at failure is longer in paperboard FRP than others. The bending modulus and bending strength are summarized in figure 6.

Figure 6 Bending results

From bending modulus comparison, it is easy to see that the carbon hybrid FRP has highest bending modulus on both MD and TD. The modulus of carbon hybrid FRP in MD and TD are 11.5 GPa and 6.94 GPa respectively. For bending strength it is very close between paperboard FRP and carbon hybrid FRP.

The fracture observation of specimens after bending test is shown in figure 7. Due to most of the fibers are distributed in MD, the cracks are attend to propagate in MD during bending test.

Figure 7 Fracture of bending specimens

3.3 Tensile test for drilled hole specimens

In this study the notched strength was used to evaluate the notched property of specimens with drilled holes. The calculation of notched strength is according to formula (1).

$$\sigma_N = \frac{P}{t * (W - D)} \quad (1)$$

Where, σ_N is notched strength; P is maximum load during tensile test; t is thickness of specimens, W is width of specimens and D is the diameter of drilled holes. The comparison between unnotched and notched strength is shown in figure 8. The results indicate that the decreasing ratio of notched strength from unnotched strength ratio is higher in MD compared with TD specimens which is considered that the material in MD is more sensitivity compared with TD.

Figure 8 Strength comparison between unnotched specimens and notched specimens

The fracture of three kinds of composite with drilled hole is shown figure 9. From the figure it can be seen that two cracks are regularly located on both side of the notched specimens. It is difficult to distinguish different fracture characteristic. The detailed observation was conducted and explains in scanning electron microscope (SEM) observation section.

Figure 9 Fracture characteristics of notched specimen

3.4 Characteristic distance

The definition of characteristic distance is illustrated with figure 10. The characteristic distance was obtained according the point stress criterion (whitney and Nuismer, 1974) [2]. In the point-stress failure criteria, the characteristic distance (d_0) is the length from the hole edge to the point where the stress equals to unnotched strength when the notched specimen carries maximum load.

Figure 10 Definition of characteristic distance

In the previous study, it was found that this parameter could be used to evaluate sensitivity of materials to circular hole [3]. In this research, the stress distribution was calculated by finite element method (MSC.Marc). The calculation results is shown in figure 11. The results revealed that the specimens in MD has lower value compared with TD which means that MD is more sensitive to drilled hole when it carries tension action. Carbon hybrid composite materials expressed high difference between MD and TD compared with other materials.

Figure 11 Calculation results of characteristic distance

3.5 Izod impact test

The result of Izod test is shown in figure 12. The comparison results indicate that the carbon hybrid composite has the highest Izod impact strength. The Izod strength of carbon hybrid fiber is 13.4 KJ/m² and 7.30 KJ/m² in MD and TD which were 202% and 110% higher compared with paperboard FRP. Although paperboard has an excellent static property, it is still has a big difference with synthetic fibers. And a hybrid form with carbon fiber is a good choice.

Figure 12 Comparison of Izod impact strength

The fracture observation after Izod test is shown in figure 13. From this results, several carbon bundles were pulled out. This is a negative effect to the mechanical property as the distribution of carbon is not good.

Figure 13 SEM observation of Izod specimens

3.5 SEM observation

The SEM observation was also carried out on notched specimens. The figure 14 was selected to explain this results. From this results, near-hole area and far from-hole area was distinguished. The fracture section in near-hole area is more regular compared with far from-hole area which was consider high stress concentration caused this phenomenon. As the crack propagating, the stress concentration became weaker and formed far form-hole area. The high magnification photos of near holes area and far form holes area are also shown here. However it is difficult to find difference from these photos.

Figure 14 SEM observation of carbon specimens with a drilled hole

4 CONCLUSIONS

In this study, the PE fibers, chopped carbon fibers and jute fibers were used to fabricate hybrid paperboard. Combined with unsaturated polyester resin, paperboard FRP, carbon hybrid FRP and jute hybrid FRP were fabricated and the mechanical property was investigated and compared, the following conclusion was summarized.

1. Paperboard FRP expressed higher tensile property and binding property compared with other materials.
2. Due to the manufacture process of paperboard, there three kinds of materials expressed obvious anisotropic property.
3. From the tensile test of drilled holes specimens and the calculation of characteristic distance, specimens expressed high sensitive in MD.
4. In the impact test carbon hybrid FRP has the best performance.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The support to this research from DAIWA ITAGAMI CO. LTD which was establishment is March, 1952 in Osaka is gratefully acknowledged.

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